

ANTENNA & STATION DESIGN CHARACTERISTICS at K7NC

11-Apr-24

To: hamsci.seqp@gmail.com

Re: HamSCI 2024 GSSC Entry

From: Jim Boardman K7NC, Grid CN87sm, North End of Vashon Island WA, USA

Rig: Yaesu FTdx10

- Tx RF power at 15 watts
- Coupled to G5RV antenna using internal tuner via...
- Heathkit HM-2140 to monitor VSWR (approx. 1:2.5 on 8-Apr-24)
- Protocol WSPR using WSJT-X, TX set at 100% from 8-Apr-24 13:08 UTC until 8-Apr-24 23:10 UTC

Antenna: G5RV

- Transmission Line: 100 ft LMR400
- VSWR at 14.095 (WSPR segment) was about 1:2.2 (measured by RigExpert AA-600 on 30-Oct-23)

- Design Diagram:

Antenna directional headings of ends: NNE at left, SSW at right

- Google Earth view of installation location at 10619 SW Cowan Rd, Vashon, WA 98070
 - GE screenshot is skewed CCW from North by about 30 degrees

